

BLENDLED LEARNING AS A WAY OF ENHANCING THE EFFICIENCY OF DISTANCE LEARNING

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Annotation: *This is thesis analyzes the concept of blended learning. The concept of blended learning is based on a learning theory that adapts to multimedia-enhanced learning environments. Blended learning means different things to different people. The word "blended" means mixed or combined. The term blended learning is still vague and forms a conceptual framework.*

Key words: *teaching method, blended learning, educational technologies, student activity.*

Today, higher education institutions are forced to adapt to the challenges of the world's economic, social, cultural and epidemiological problems after rapid developments in society. Perhaps, it is essential for higher education institutions to provide students with personalized education and to meet their needs for quality education, despite natural and social disasters. Today, in the context of digital transformation, the development of distance and blended learning technologies, which have become especially important during the coronavirus pandemic, is leading to corresponding changes in the organization of educational activities and the interaction of subjects of the educational process. Thus, according to a study conducted by the G2R group, led by Imed Bushrik, PhD, online learning has become a safe and beneficial option for the continuity of education, as the COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted the personal and professional worlds. The development of distance learning technologies contributes to the diversification and spread of blended learning, which is considered acceptable for teaching and learning in secondary schools and higher education institutions. However, the issue of choosing a blended learning model in a higher education institution requires a separate study. After all, it is necessary to choose the most successful and correct organization of blended learning, taking into account the characteristics of the educational institution and its experience in digital education.

This task involves analyzing existing models of blended learning, changing them or developing your own model of organizing blended learning in a higher education institution, and evaluating the results of implementing the developed model.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Effective professional development of students. The problem of modeling and organizing blended learning in higher education institutions to ensure is studied by K. Andersson, P. Appiah-Kubi, N. Balyk, E. Basile, N. Kushnir, L. Kuzmich, D. Logofatu., S. Litvinova, M. McCabe, V. Oleksyuk, Osipova, K. Shentyurk, O. Spirin, S. Sidorenko, N. Valko, K. Zuhri and other researchers. . C. Shentyurk presents the results of a study on how the blended approach to teaching and learning affects the academic activity and qualifications of 21st century teachers trained in the principles and methods at the university. He proposed a generalized model of blended learning, which is an intersection of face-to-face and virtual learning. The researcher found that blended learning experiences have a significant impact on students' long-term learning and twenty-first century skills. P. Appiah-Kubi et al. describe a study that was initiated to examine the level of engagement of engineering technology students with online learning materials using ZOOM and a learning management system. The researchers noted that engineering technology programs include many laboratory and practical modules.

Thus, it is necessary to ensure that students continue to learn despite the limitations of the online mode. They found that students who mastered the learning materials at a high level in blended courses achieved better results.

O. Spirin et al. use a cloud (complex) approach to learning by combining computer networks. Their learning method is to use an integrated academic cloud that includes the Apache CloudStack and EVE-NG Community platforms to support teamwork. The researchers discuss some methods of blended learning, including: a combination of face-to-face and distance learning, collaboration of group members, development of teamwork skills, heterogeneous (random) grouping, the combined use of individual and peer assessment, monitoring of student performance, task completion, a guided approach, and feedback where necessary. The results of experimental research show that blended learning allows students to use the technological methods of the academic program (cloud) to more effectively achieve their learning goals.

An approach to developing a learning design model for mobile blended learning in higher education is described by I. K. Suartama, P. Setyosari, S. Sultani, and S. Ulfa . The researchers developed a mobile blended learning project for a university Media Education course, the purpose of which is to provide students with knowledge and skills in designing, developing, using, evaluating, and evaluating media in education. The developed model is presented in the form of a matrix of learning objectives, learning stages, and features of the

Moodle LMS mobile application. The researchers formulate 8 learning objectives based on the learning objectives of the revised Bloom's taxonomy. They consider blended learning to consist of three stages: 1) before the lesson (online); 2) in the classroom/on-site (offline); 3) after the lesson (online). Thus, they propose activities for each learning objective and each stage.

A. Adel and J. Dayan [9] describe the design of a blended learning system for universities in New Zealand. This is a general learning model that combines digital technology with traditional education. Its central part is a social networking site, where all other components (login session, e-learning, classroom teaching, virtual support) are interconnected. Wahjono et al. present a blended learning model based on the implementation of a semester credit system. It combines three main stages, namely planning, organization and teaching-methodical process. The planning stage consists, in particular, of student enrollment, program selection, and class grouping. The organizational stage includes, in particular, the preparation of guidance documents, analysis and mapping of key competencies, and development of a management system.

These modern technical tools further improve the quality of education and facilitate quick and easy delivery of material. Office programs, graphic editors and other computer programs used in the lesson process are also included in the software and are convenient to use during the lesson. For example, we can use Easy Quizy, My Test, Quiz Maker, Hot Potatoes programs to test the knowledge of students and pupils during the lesson. We can create a presentation in Power Point and use it during the lesson, prepare educational materials in Word, store information about the group led by the teacher in Access, prepare various tables in Excel, and enter the lesson schedule. It is advisable to use Google's capabilities to manage online documents. Using Google documents, Google spreadsheets and Google presentation applications, it will be possible to prepare online electronic resources and educational materials. It is also advisable to use artificial intelligence systems in the teaching process: to them, robots based on robotics, their boards and platforms, and programming can be used to give lectures during the lesson, as an assistant in conducting conferences, as a robot to monitor students sitting in the library and preparing lessons, such robots have entered the educational process.

They register on the site on the Moodle learning platform, they can use it with their login and password, that is, the use of authentication and identification processes is always useful when working in the online system. Each teacher must know how to use software tools, computer programs, and various tools, based on their competence. By pedagogical information and communication technology competence, we mean the teacher's

ability to apply them to the teaching process, based on his skills and knowledge of using technical means, computer programs, and their relevance to science and subjects.

These discoveries allow us to develop and store huge amounts of information and quickly distribute them through communication networks. Connecting computers to each other and setting them up to communicate with each other allows us to create a new powerful technological system - network information systems using a common protocol. They connect people, their homes and offices and in a very short time develop and perform a huge number of tasks. This radically changes the nature of information use and the structure of communication. At the same time, computer networks have convenient opportunities for communication with all points of the globe.

The future teacher's deep knowledge and ability to work effectively depends on the extent to which he has formed sufficient theoretical and practical knowledge of the foundations of a certain science, and the ability to effectively use new pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process.

It is of great importance to improve the quality of training pedagogical personnel in bachelor's and master's specialties, to inform students about the latest results of scientific development. Ensuring the rapid introduction of scientific and technical innovations into the content of curricula creates a basis for the formation of modern knowledge and a scientific worldview in students.

In addition, modern teaching technologies and related methodological approaches create good conditions for the relatively easy and solid formation of necessary knowledge, important laws and many fundamental concepts in future teachers.

Modern trends in the use of information technologies in the educational process. As is known, education is given great importance in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Indeed, the most important factor determining the prosperity of any state is personnel. The reforms being carried out consistently on the basis of the Law “On Education” and the National Program for Personnel Training are a vivid example of this. In order to educate a well-rounded, comprehensively developed, broad-minded generation and integrate it into the world community, teaching foreign languages is currently considered one of the priority tasks of our state. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1875 of 2012 “On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages” defined the tasks in this direction.

These include tasks such as training foreign language teachers, the widespread use of information and media technologies in education, and the use of interactive methods in the classroom.

In the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 23, 2013 No. PQ-1971 “On measures to improve the activities of the Uzbek State University of World Languages”, the Uzbek State University of Languages is tasked with training highly qualified teachers of foreign languages for general secondary, secondary specialized, and vocational educational institutions who are qualified to use modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies for teaching foreign languages. The purpose of the subject "Information

Technologies" is aimed at implementing these priority tasks.

The potential of information technologies in the effective teaching of foreign languages is very great, and therefore its role in the training of pedagogical personnel is special. Along with knowledge of information technologies, technical and software tools used in teaching foreign languages, skills such as technologies for creating and processing multimedia resources in teaching foreign languages, the formation of personal electronic educational resources, designing electronic courses in teaching foreign languages, systems for assessing student knowledge, the use of Internet technologies in teaching foreign languages, distance learning technologies and methods of their organization, video conferencing, and the organization of mass online open courses (Coursera, edX, Khan Academy, MIT Open Course Ware) are of great importance in pedagogical activity. Using practical software tools, knowing how to create electronic textbooks, simulators, virtual laboratory exercises with their help, having the ability to create electronic educational and methodological materials in Microsoft Word, Excel, Power Point and other programs, as well as creating electronic didactic materials using Web technologies and using them in the educational process are considered important factors in determining the skills of a foreign language teacher.

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